

Inoculum efficiency in sheath blight as affected by contact frequency, leaf wetness regime, and nitrogen supply

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An experimental design was developed at IRRI to study components of rice sheath blight (ShB) epidemics, caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kühn (IRRN 18(3): 42-43, 1993). This design allows measurement of responses of the pathosystem to various stimuli, representing crop management or environmental factors. One response is the ratio of the density of daughter lesions on trap plants to the density of mother lesions on inoculated plants, which we term inoculum efficiency (IE). We report here effects of crop density, leaf wetness, and N supply on IE.

The methodology involves two basic components: a quadrat of 3 × 3 hills where the disease is artificially established by inoculating the hills with a rice grain and hull mixture colonized by the fungus, and a healthy trap plant that probes the conduciveness of the quadrat to ShB at its center. Inoculation of the quadrat hills was done at maximum tillering stage by placing on each of them 5 g of inoculum at the leaf level and another 5 g at the base of the tillers. IR72, a semidwarf, high-yielding variety, was used in all experiments. Unless otherwise specified, all experiments had a 20- × 20-cm spacing between hills and a fertilizer rate of 120 kg N/ha. All were conducted in the screenhouse using a randomized complete block design with three successive batches of trap plants and the quadrats as the basic experimental unit.

The experiment addressing contact frequency was conducted in Sep-Oct 1992. Seedlings were transplanted 14 d after sowing at 18- × 18-cm spacing. They were later transplanted during maximum tillering stage according to preset spacing treatments: 15 × 15 cm, 15 × 20 cm, 20 × 20 cm, and 25 × 25 cm.

The effect of leaf wetness duration was analyzed in the dry season (Feb-Apr

1993) with five leaf wetness regimes as treatments: permanently dry (T0), wet for one night (T1), wet for two consecutive nights (T2), wet for three consecutive nights (T3), and permanently wet (PW). The experiment had five replications. Leaf wetness was obtained during the night with water sprays prior to caging the quadrats with plastic stapled onto wooden frames at 1700 h. Permanent wetness was achieved by continuous water sprays during the day and caging at night.

The effect of N supply on the crop was analyzed during Jun-Jul 1992. The experiment had eight replications. Trap plants were grown in plots with three N input levels: no N (N0), 60 kg N/ha (N1), and 90 kg N/ha (N2). At maximum tillering stage, the trap plants were transferred to the center of the quadrats that had been fertilized at the rate of 120 kg N/ha.

At the start of a 3-d probing period in all experiments, trap plants were placed into the quadrats. One hill per quadrat was randomly chosen and five of its tillers were sampled to measure their leaf and stem area (cm²). The lesion density on the quadrat (LDq, dimension: [lesion number/area]) was determined by taking the average number of infection points on all the leaves and stems of each tiller.

After each probing, the trap plants were removed from the quadrat and potted. The leaf and stem areas were measured from a sample of five tillers, and the lesion density on the trap plant (LD, dimension: [lesion number/area]) was taken by counting the number of infection points on the leaves and stems of all the tillers after a 3-d incubation period.

Inoculum efficiency: $IE = LD/LDq$ (dimension: [lesion number/lesion number]) was calculated for each probing period. It represents the progeny-parent ratio in terms of lesions present on the quadrat and on the trap plants. Because it involves lesion densities and not lesion numbers, it takes into account the differences in area of the source and trap plants across the different treatments and batches. IE was analyzed using repeated measures ANOVA with batch as the repeated measures factor (see table). IE generally declines across batches,

1. Relationship between plant spacing (a), leaf wetness regime (b), and N supply (c) and the inoculum efficiency in sheath blight. IRRI, 1992-93.

^a T0 = permanently dry, T1 = wet for one night, T2 = wet for two consecutive nights, T3 = wet for three consecutive nights, and PW = permanently wet.

suggesting that the number of infectious lesions decreased over time.

Higher contact frequency facilitated disease spread as shown by the significantly higher IE (see table, $P < 0.01$) in

Repeated measures ANOVA for inoculum efficiency (IE) in ShB as affected by contact frequency, leaf wetness regime, and N supply to the crop.^a IRR1, 1992-93.

Source of variation	Effect of contact frequency			Effect of leaf wetness			Effect of N supply		
	df	MS	F	df	MS	F	df	MS	F
Replication (R)	4	0.0023	3.60*	4	0.0089	1.55	7	0.0113	0.76
Treatment (T)	3	0.0047	7.47**	4	0.0509	8.84**	2	0.0855	5.80*
Error (a)	12	0.0006		16	0.0058		14	0.0148	
Batch (B)	2	0.0079	9.88**	2	0.2187	23.26**	2	0.1194	9.48**
Linear (B _L)	(1)	0.0148	18.50**	(1)	0.3329	29.46**	(1)	0.2327	15.91**
Quadratic (B _Q)	(1)	0.0010	2.63	(1)	0.1045	14.12**	(1)	0.0061	0.57
B × T	6	0.0002	0.25	8	0.0178	1.89	4	0.0136	1.89
B _L × T	(3)	0.0003	0.23	(4)	0.0269	2.38	(2)	0.0166	1.13
B _Q × T	(3)	0.0001	0.26	(4)	0.0087	1.18	(2)	0.0105	0.99
Error (b)	32	0.0008		40	0.0094		42	0.0126	
E _{B_L}	(16)	0.0013		(20)	0.0113		(21)	0.0146	
E _{B_Q}	(16)	0.0004		(20)	0.0074		(21)	0.0106	
Total	59			74			71		

^aFisher ratio values followed by * or ** are significant at P < 0.05 or 0.01, respectively.

close plant spacings than in wide spacings (Fig. 1a). At closer spacing, inoculum from infected tissues is more easily mobilized to healthy tissues of the

same or adjacent plants via mycelial growth. IE was significantly higher (see table, P < 0.01) in the interrupted leaf wetness treatments (T3) than in the

continuously dry or in continuously wet treatments (Fig. 1b): alternate dry and wet periods enhance disease progress. While leaf wetness is necessary for the survival and growth of mycelium, dry periods may enhance contacts between hyphae and plant surfaces, thus facilitating penetration.

IE declined with increased N supply. IE at 60 and 90 kg N/ha (resulting in 1.8 and 2.2% N content in the leaves, respectively) was significantly lower (see table, P < 0.05) than unfertilized plants (1.7% N content), with a twofold difference between the fertilized and nonfertilized treatments (Fig. 1c). Another independent experiment (not shown) was conducted, which led to the same conclusion. While N content decreases IE, it may enhance other components of the ShB monocycle, such as the rate of lesion expansion, latent period, and infectious period of ShB. These effects are currently being investigated. ■

Considering rice quality factors in farm management decisions

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Ignoring the relationship between inputs and quality when making rice farm management decisions may have negative implications. We compared, at the farm level, maximum returns above variable cost (RAVC_R) levels and associated ratoon crop nitrogen (N) levels using traditional profit maximization techniques that ignore rice quality factors with results for modified maximization techniques that incorporate rice quality determining factors, such as head yield, milling yield, and grade.

The data used in the analysis are from a three-year survey (1987-89) of Texas rice producers' main and ratoon crop production practices. Data for 464 ratoon-cropped ricefields covering more than 22,000 ha were collected. Quantity

and quality production functions were specified ex ante by rice research scientists and specialists of the Texas Agricultural Experiment Station, Texas Agricultural Extension Service, and U. S. Department of Agriculture at Beaumont, Texas. Multiple regression analysis was used to determine the impact of rice production inputs on rice yields and quality.

Scientists' hypotheses about the relationship between N and ratoon quality are primarily drawn from work done on the main crop. High rates applied to the main crop have been shown to be positively associated with higher harvest grain moisture contents, thus N is not hypothesized to directly affect quality when rice is harvested at the proper moisture. For the ratoon crop, moisture content may vary more widely than that of the main crop because retillering of the ratoon crop is often uneven. Thus, it is hypothesized that high N rates contribute to higher yields but may contribute to lower quality.

Statistically significant estimated relationships between N and ratoon field yield and N and ratoon head yield are presented in the figure for producers

using semidwarf varieties irrigated with high pH water. Ratoon crop field and head yield increase with higher levels of N until 90 kg/ha. Above that application level, ratoon head yields decrease while field yields continue to increase, resulting in a conflicting relationship. This relationship may be due to mechanically harvesting rice at improper grain moisture content; however, uneven maturity, ruts in the field, weather, and N rates above those used in previous experimental studies may hinder the replication of previous experimental research. The results, however, do support current Texas recommendations of no more than 112 kg N/ha for semidwarf varieties during the ratoon production phase.

Rice producers in the USA are paid not only for quantity but also quality. To determine the impact of recognizing the relationship between rice quality and input usage, yield and quality production functions (head yield, milling yield, and grade) were used to calculate RAVC_R. RAVC_R-maximizing levels of N were determined using a static \$0.15/kg nonquality-dependent rice price and a quality-dependent rice price. With regard to sensitivity of results to N input cost